

Speculation of Quantum Bound State Thermodynamics Part III

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Historically statistical mechanics was developed for gasses for which there are very large numbers of molecules (i.e. on the order of 10^{23} rd power). As a result factorial schemes were developed to count the number of arrangements possible, the \ln taken of this result and Stirling's approximation for large N applied. The Shannon's entropy form $S/(-k) = \sum_i P(e_i) \ln(P(e_i))$ is consistent with this large N approach. Furthermore, large N statistical mechanics was linked to thermodynamics, in particular the first law $dE = TdS - PdV$. Surprisingly then, statistical mechanical results were applied to systems with small numbers of particles (e.g. a nucleus with about 100 nucleons etc).

In Parts I and II we argued that the first law of thermodynamics describes two separate kinds of changes associated with energy changes. The second, work, is linked to the change of a mechanical parameter such as the volume of a box etc. The energy of a bound quantum particle in a box with an infinite potential is proportional to n^2/L^2 . Thus we argued that a pure quantum bound state may also be associated with the first law of thermodynamics with changes in L with n , the energy level, held constant representing pure work.

We further argued that for a bound state two classical like probabilities exist $P(x) = W(x)W(x)$ and $P(p) = a(p)a(p)$ where $W(x) = \text{wavefunction} = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ with $P(x)$ being proportional to $1/L$ and $P(p)$ to L . For a quantum adiabatic transformation (i.e. changing L with n staying constant) the term $dS = 0$. If one wishes to create S from $P(x)$ and $P(p)$ and desires linearity i.e. $S = S_p(n) + S_x$, then $S_p = \int dp P(p) \ln(P(p))$ and $S_x = \int dx P(x) \ln(P(x))$ is a solution.

If one next considers a quantum wavefunction for two levels $W(x,t) = a(1) \exp(-iE_1 t) W_1(x) + a(2) \exp(-iE_2 t) W_2(x)$ with $E = \sum_n e_n P(e_n)$ where $W_n = a(n)a(n)$, one may again utilize the first law of thermodynamics. In Parts I and II we carried over the entropy form $P(e_i) \ln(P(e_i))$. In this note we wish to argue that this form follows at the two energy level picture by considerations of a function which consists entirely of probabilities i.e. $P(e_i)$ and is linear in the sense that such a function for two identical two state systems should yield $S_1 + S_2$ as the first law should apply to each system. Furthermore $P(e_i)$ should be a function of $P(e_i/T)$ where T is a parameter which behaves as $1/L^2$ because e_i is proportional to $1/L^2$. In this way any function of $P(e_i)$ remains unchanged under a quantum adiabatic transformation for which i 's stay constant, but L changes. As a result, the entropy at the quantum level seems to follow from such arguments and not from large N approximations of factorial counting approaches.

In large N situations it is argued that $P(e_i) = C(T) \exp(-e_i/T)$ follows from maximizing S with respect to the form of $P(e_i)$ subject to constant average energy. For small N situations (e.g. the 2 level example) one may solve $\sum_i e_i d(a(i)a(i)) = T dS$ directly without maximization. The maximization approach follows directly from $dE = TdS$ (work=0) because $dE = \sum e_i dP(e_i)$ in such scenarios. This is of the form of a Lagrange constraint This has been pointed out in Part II. In this note, we argue that the maximization of entropy is not needed at all. For $dE = \sum e_i dP(e_i)$ and the \ln form of entropy $P(e_i)$ is the inverse function of \ln .

Thus we argue that linearity and not large N arguments are enough to obtain Shannon's form of entropy and that this \ln form suggests $P(e_i/T) = C(T) \exp(-e_i/T)$ if $dE = \sum e_i dP(e_i) = TdS$

(for $dW=0$). Thus maximization of entropy subject to constant average energy is also not needed (although it does follow mathematically from $dE=TdS$.)

First Law of Thermodynamics and Entropy for a Pure Quantum Bound State

It seems the first law of thermodynamics and Shannon's form of entropy exist already at the level of a quantum bound state. In Parts I and II we considered a particle in a box with infinite potential walls. The time-independent Schrodinger equation yields E_n values which usually also depends on a mechanical parameter. For the box it is L , but for an oscillator it is k , the spring constant. One may have an energy change due a change in n or the mechanical parameter with the latter being linked to work. In addition, if one may write the time-independent Schrodinger equation in terms of a variable $y=bx$ where b is the mechanical parameter and E becomes E/bb then $P(x) = 1/b W(y)W(y)$ and $P(p) = b a(y)a(y)$ where $W(x)=\text{Sum over } p a(p)\exp(ipx)$.

The first law of thermodynamics may be written as: $dE=dQ-dW$ where Q is heat and W work. For a quantum adiabatic transformation $dQ=0$ and $dE=-dW$. In such a transformation for a pure state, n remains constant and L changes. It is possible to create a function S entirely out of $P(x)$ and $P(p)$ such that L disappears and S is linear i.e. $S=S_p+S_x$. In particular:

$$S = \int dp dx P(x)P(p) \ln\{P(x)P(p)\} = \int dp P(p)\ln(P(p)) + \int dx P(x)\ln(P(x)) \quad ((1))$$

A mechanical parameter such as L for the box or k the spring constant disappears in such a case. S , however, does not have units of energy and so needs to be multiplied by a constant for a given n . This constant is called T temperature. Thus, Shannon's entropy and the first law of thermodynamics seem to exist for a pure quantum bound state.

Two Level System

Next one may consider a two level system with:

$$W(x,t) = a(1) \exp(-ie_1 t) W_1(x) + a(2) \exp(-ie_2 t) W_2(x) \quad ((2)) \text{ with } E_{ave} = \text{Sum over } i e_i P(e_i) \quad ((3))$$

((3)) the average energy is expressed directly in terms of $P(e_i)$ which is different from the pure bound state case. Nevertheless the first law of thermodynamics should still hold as should the notion of a quantum adiabatic transformation leaving i 's constant still holds. For an adiabatic transformation

$$dQ=0 = \text{Sum over } i e_i dP(e_i) \quad \text{so } dP(e_i) = 0 \text{ if } L \text{ changes, but } i \text{ stays constant.}$$

As argued in Part II, e_i is proportional to $1/LL$ so a solution is to have $P(e_i/T)$ where T is proportional to $1/LL$ as well. The question which arises is: What should entropy be in this case?

In the pure bound state case it was $S_x = -\int dx P(x) \ln(P(x))$ and $S_p = -\int dp P(p) \ln(P(p))$. In Part II we argued that for consistency, one may use the same form with $P(e_i)$, but in this note we try to see if there are further arguments for this form.

Additive Entropy

In the above section we consider a two level quantum bound system for a single particle. Imagine that one has two such systems with independent probabilities $P_1(e_i)$ and $P_2(e_i)$. Then one may write $P(1 \text{ in } e_i \text{ and } 2 \text{ in } e_i) = P_1(e_i)P_2(e_i)$. If one only wishes to consider thermal properties i.e. L remains constant for each, the one might consider $d(E_1+E_2) = T dS$. In such a case, one would want $S=S_1+S_2$, but in the pure bound state case the Shannon's entropy form was chosen to give this result. Thus $S = -\sum_i P_1(e_i)P_2(e_i) \ln\{P_1(e_i)P_2(e_i)\} = S_1 + S_2$ as desired. Thus the $P(e_i) \ln(P(e_i))$ is retained for these reasons.

Consideration of TdS

The first law of thermodynamics $dE=dQ-dW$. dQ for a pure bound state one may change n holding L constant (particle in a box). For the two level system $dQ = \sum_i e_i dP(e_i/T)$. This begs the question: why does one need a function S which is only composed of $P(e_i)$ while $E = \sum_i e_i P(e_i/T)$ i.e. is mixed? The \ln form in $S = -\sum_i P(e_i) \ln(P(e_i))$ was chosen to ensure linearity i.e. $S=S_1+S_2$ both for the pure bound state and for the two level system. For this to be consistent with dE it seems that $P(e_i/T) = C(T) \exp(-e_i/T)$. No maximization of the \ln of arrangements is necessary. This form of probability follows immediately from dE with e_i left unchanged and the form of entropy. In other words $P(e_i)$ is the inverse function of the entropy function \ln .

(Note In parts I and II we incorporate the entropy of the pure state and use $\exp(-e_i/T) \exp(S_{\text{pure}})$ where $S=S_p(n)+S_x$ from the pure bound state. Here we drop this term for convenience.)

Let us consider this in more detail for the one particle - two level system of a box with infinite potential walls and a system with N levels where N is large. Choose $n=1$ and $n=2$. Then:

$$\sum_i P(e_i) = 1 \quad \text{so } 1/C(T) = \exp(-e_1/T) + \exp(-e_2/T) \quad ((3)) \quad \text{where } e_1=b \text{ and } e_2=4b$$

$$\text{And } P(e_1) = \exp(-b/T) / \{\exp(-b/T) + \exp(-4b/T)\} \quad \text{which is the value given in (1).}$$

This may also be obtained using: $\sum_i e_i dP(e_i) = -T dS$.

For N levels $P(e_i/T) = C(T) \exp(-e_i/T)$ and one may formally show as was done in Part II that $dE=TdS$ holds.

Maximization of Entropy Subject to Constant Average Energy

For large N systems approximations are made to arrive at Shannon's entropy i.e. $S/(-k) = \sum_i P(i) \ln(P(i))$. For the factorial approach Stirling's approximation is used. Next it is argued that one should maximize entropy subject to a constant average energy. As argued in Part II, this follows immediately from the first law of thermodynamics:

$$dE = TdS \text{ for } dW=0 \text{ because } dE = \sum_i e_i dP(e_i)$$

In the previous section, however, we argue that no maximization is needed. $C(T) \exp(-e_i/T)$ is a solution simply because it is the inverse of the \ln function which appears in the entropy expression.

Conclusion

In conclusion we try to make two points. First, Shannon's form of entropy which arguably appears for a pure bound state is utilized to ensure linearity. For the pure bound state this means $S_p + S_x = S$ which ensures that mechanical parameters disappear from the entropy expression. This guarantees that $dS=0$ if one changes a mechanical parameter, but leaves n , the energy level, constant as in a quantum adiabatic transformation. In Part II we carried over this form of entropy to a two level single particle quantum system (for a particle in a box with infinite potential walls). Here we argue that \ln is again needed for linearity because one may have two identical two particle systems (independent) and an overall S should break into $S_1 + S_2$ because $E = E_1 + E_2$.

The second point concerns the idea of maximization of entropy subject to the constraint of constant average energy which we demonstrated in Part II and argued was equivalent to $dE = TdS$ for $dW=0$. Here we argue that one does not need maximization at all because the form $dE = TdS$ ($dW=0$) for $dE = \sum_i e_i dP(e_i)$ suggests that $\ln(P(e_i)) = C(T) \exp(-e_i/T)$. We show that this is the case for the two level system and any N level system. (The full demonstration for the N level is already included in Part II.)

Thus the idea that Shannon's entropy follows by considering the \ln of factorial arrangements for large N with approximation methods such as Stirling's approximation followed by maximization of entropy subject to constant average energy does not seem to be the case for quantum thermodynamics. The same results are obtained without these approaches as discussed in Parts I, II and III. We argue that one may start with a quantum pure state and move to large systems and that the main ideas of thermodynamics and Shannon's entropy already exist for the quantum bound state and two level system.

References

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